

Exploring the Factors Influencing the Study Habits of Grade 10 Students in Science at Jolo, Sulu

Shallemar C. Pelayo¹
1 – Sulu State College

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Abstract

Basically, this study is limited to explore the different factors influencing the study habits of grade 10 students in Science enrolled during the school year 2018-2019. This study was conducted in the Division of Sulu. Of the many schools in Sulu, the researcher focused on the three (3) junior high schools located at the territory of the town of Jolo. The variables in this study were the factors influencing the study habits of the respondents classified according to home, school, teacher and peer. Respondent's demographic profile in terms of gender and parents' income was included as well together with their academic achievement in Science.

The research findings in this study revealed the following among the grade 10 students of Jolo, Sulu: The demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender, reflected that, female composed the majority of the respondents having 109 female which is equivalent to 72.7% of the total number of respondents, while in terms of parents' income, majority of the respondents' parents' income ranges from Php 10,000 to Php

29,999; Factors Influencing the Study Habits of the Respondents: It was found that School factor received a weighted mean of 3.56 (SD = 0.45), while as Teacher factor gained a weighted mean of 4.48 (SD = 0.57) and finally, Peer factor received an average weighted mean of 3.55 (SD = 0.70) indicating a descriptive rating of "Agree" in these factors while Home factors yielded a weighted mean of 3.32 (SD = 0.45) further indicating a descriptive rating of "Moderately Agree". A significant difference was found on the study habits of the respondents based on the respondents' demographic profile. Similarly, this study recorded significant difference between the study habits of the respondents in Science and their academic achievement in the said subject.

Based on the result of this study, it can be inferred that, a good study habit helps a student achieve academic success. It can also be noted that the study habits of a student are influenced by different factors such as home, school, teacher and peer.

Keywords: *study habits, academic achievement, Science education, influencing factors, Grade 10 students*

INTRODUCTION

Science serves as one of the weapons and strengths of an individual in adapting change, because it prepares him to equip him with the necessary knowledge, skills and even attitudes that he will eventually need in facing a certain situation. This is the reason why students must not take Science subject for granted, instead, they must grab the opportunity to let their ability be developed and enhanced more, through the concepts they will be learning.

In Junior High School, Science is taken up as integrated subject, as Biology, Earth Science, Chemistry and Physics being taught with varying topics in every grade level. On this note, the possibility for lack of depth in specific Science field is a disadvantage, because students might not have the same level of mastery in individual fields. However, to help students overcome this disadvantage, having an effective study habit is suggested.

Study habits are the student's ways of study whether systematic, efficient or inefficient (Good, 1973) cited by Moha (2018) and was also perceived by Abid (2006) as the determinants of student's academic performance.

The study habit of a student can be determined by the different factors he experiences at home, school, with his teachers and peers. In order for a student to develop a good study habit, these factors must be taken into consideration because they can also lead to the development of poor study habit. According to various studies, study habit determines the academic achievement of a student. Thus, failure to consider the factors affecting the study habits of a student may manifest low level of academic success.

Palacio in her document, "Helping students develop good study habits" retrieved at www.slidesahre.net noted that, the responsibility for developing good study habits is the equal responsibility of teachers, students and parents. Teachers should only give achievable tasks that would encourage the students to enhance their critical thinking and creativity. Students must learn the value of serious study, how to work independently and to manage their time wisely. At home, a conducive place for learning must be secured by parents.

The influence of their friends is also among the factors that contribute to the development of the kind of study habits they may have. According to some researchers, the kind of friends a student mingles determine his academic success. With this finding it would lead to saying that friends indeed can influence the academic performance of a student.

This research was conducted to serve as an eye-opener to individuals who affect the lives of students as well as their academic performances and achievements.

In this study, the researcher focused on four factors that influence the study habits of the respondents, namely home, school, teacher and peer. This was conducted to determine the extent of the influence of these factors in the study habits of the respondents and their relationship to their academic achievement in Science.

RELATED LITERATURE

Study habits pertain to the study routines, including frequency of studying sessions, making review materials based on lectures and studying in a conducive environment. Good (1973) defined the terms study habits as "the student's ways of study whether systematic, efficient or inefficient." and was also perceived by Adeyemi (2014) as an important factor in student's academic achievement. Furthermore, Adesemowo (2000) noted in her study that a major cause of underachievement at school is poor study habits, even a brilliant student can underachieve if he has faulty study habit. Hughes (2014) shares her advice on how to incorporate good study habits: (1) Budget time carefully; (2) Keep your emotions check; (3) Maintain a positive mindset about priorities; (4) Use all available resources; (5) Break tasks into manageable chunks; (6) Appoint a study boss; and (7) Learn from mistakes.

The family has an important role in the education of children as reported by Adeyemi (2014). Children from alcoholic homes often perceive stress, feel insecure, angry and frustrated and this affects

their academic performance, he added. In a similar study by Kingdom (1996) as cited by Adeyemi (2014) it was posited that home factors have a significant correlation with students' academic achievement. Palacio (2011) noted that, students who develop good study habits at school increase the potential to complete their assignments successfully and to learn the material they are studying. Furthermore, they can also reduce the amount of time spent on homework.

Adesoji and Oladele (2003) as cited by Adeyemi and Adeyemi (2014) conducted a study on student and teacher related variables as determinants of secondary school students' academic achievement in Chemistry in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study revealed that study habit and attitude had no significant and direct relationship with secondary school students' academic achievement. According to the researchers this is not to say that they did not have effect, but their effects are not significant particularly in the presence of teacher variables as teacher experience, teacher qualifications and teacher's age.

Siegler (2006) defined peer as a person who has equal standing with another or others. He added, influence is the power to affect the way someone or something develops, behaves or thinks without using direct force or orders. Peers are likely to influence one another's beliefs and behavior. Burke and Sass (2008) asserted that peer effect depends on the students' ability and on the ability of peers under consideration. Peer effects tend to have similar impact when teacher-related factors are included, a result that suggest significant combined influence of peer and teacher quality on student's behavior.

Aquino (2006) mentioned that the need to improve student's study habits and attitudes is deemed necessary to improve the student's academic achievement. Accordingly, it is essential for schools to determine factors which affect these characteristics adversely, propose remedial measures and employ strategies for the development of good study habits and attitudes.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

A descriptive research design method was employed in this study. This study is purported to describe, quantify, and infer as well as to discover significant differences and relationships among variables and to allow the prediction of future events from present knowledge or phenomenon of Grade 10 students, namely:

- 1) The demographic profile of the respondents in terms of gender and parents' income;
- 2) The extent of the factors influencing the study habits of grade 10 students in Science;
- 3) The significant difference on the study habits of the respondents when data are classified according to gender and parents' income; and
- 4) The significant difference between the study habits of the respondents and their academic achievement in Science.

Grade 10 students enrolled at Jolo, Sulu were the main source of data which were quantified to answer the research questions in this study. Library and internet research were the sources of information used to enrich the theoretical and conceptual frameworks of this research. The data from the respondents was obtained through the use of questionnaires.

Data was generated using the Likert type questionnaire checklist for the factors influencing the study habits of the respondents.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Sulu, specifically at Jolo, where the three respondent-schools are located namely, Notre Dame of Jolo High School – Kasulutan, located at Gandasuli, Jolo, Sulu; Notre Dame of Jolo for Girls, located at Kasanyangan Village, Jolo, Sulu; and Sulu State College Laboratory High School, located at Walled City, Jolo, Sulu.

Respondents of the Study

The respondents of this study are the one hundred fifty (150) grade 10 students from Notre Dame of Jolo High School – Kasulitan; Notre Dame of Jolo for Girls; and Sulu State College Laboratory High School, enrolled for the school year 2018-2019.

Sampling Design

Stratified and random sampling procedure was used to select the sample respondents. The respondents were classified into three (3) strata of fifty (50) students each randomly selected at the three school-respondents.

Data gathering Procedure

The following procedures were employed in the course of data gathering:

1. After the survey questionnaire was approved and reproduced, the researcher secured permission from the different school heads of her school-respondent for the launching of the questionnaire.
2. Upon receiving the affirmative responses of the different school heads, the researcher launched her questionnaire to the respondents, requesting them to submit accomplished questionnaire as scheduled.
3. The researcher also requested the Science teachers of the respondents to furnish a copy of the respondents' grades in Science.
4. When the respondents were through answering the survey questionnaire, the researcher personally retrieved them.

Research Instrument

A survey questionnaire was the main instrument used to gather data for this study. The statements under the different factors influencing the study habits of Grade 10 students in Science, particularly under Home and School were adopted from the questionnaire used by Irlis (2005) on her research entitled, "Factors Affecting the Study Habits of the Sixth Graders of Riverside Elementary School", while statements under Teacher and Peer factors were formulated based on the experiences gathered from the students at Sulu State College Laboratory High School.

The survey questionnaire is divided into three parts. The first part is the personal data of the respondents which includes their name, gender and school. The second part is their parents' income. The third part is the different factors influencing the respondents' study habits. Under this part, it includes four factors: Home, School, Teacher and Peer. Under Home, there are 12 statements, for School, there are 10 statements, for Teacher, there are 9 statements and for Peer, there are 6 statements.

The scale used in the questionnaire is the five – point Likert – type scale as follows:

Limit	Numerical Rating	Descriptive Rating
5-4.5	5	Strongly Agree
4.49-3.5	4	Agree
3.49-2.5	3	Moderately Agree
2.49-1.5	2	Disagree
1.49-1	1	Strongly Disagree

Reliability and Validity

The questionnaire was adopted from the questionnaire used by Irlis (2005) on her research entitled, "Factors Affecting the Study Habits of the Sixth Graders of Riverside Elementary School" with established validity and reliability and some part of the questionnaire was crafted by the researcher. To suit the usability of the research instrument to the respondents, it was subjected to the perusal of at least two (2) experts from the faculty members of Sulu State College.

Statistical Treatment of Data

Descriptive and inferential statistical tools were appropriately employed in the treatment of data gathered for this study, namely:

1. For research problem number one 1, frequency counts and percentage were employed to determine the demographic profile of the respondents.
2. For research problem number two 2, mean and standard deviation were employed to determine the extent of the factors influencing the study habits of the respondents in Science.
3. For research question number 4, F-test was employed to determine the significant difference on the study habits of the respondents when data are classified according to gender and parents' income; and
4. For research problem 4, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and F-test one-way factor were employed to determine the significant difference between the study habits of the respondents and their academic achievement in Science.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This chapter deals with the results of the statistical computations and the discussion of the results justified by the related literature and studies which are collaborative or opposite findings. The sequence of the presentation of data followed the sequence of the problem as stated. The analysis of data is in tabular form.

The first research problem this study sought to answer was “*What is the profile of the respondents as to gender and parents' income?*”. As shown in table 1.1, female dominant in number can be seen at 72.7 percent (72%) compared to male at 27.3 percent (27.3%). Specifically, female in Sulu State College Laboratory High School is composed of 74 percent (74%) while male is 26 percent (26%); Notre Dame of Jolo High School-Kasulutan had 44 percent (44%) female and 56 percent male (56%); and Notre Dame of Jolo for Girls had 100 percent (100%) female since it is a school for girls only.

Table 1.1 Cross tabulation of the respondents according to Gender and School

School	Gender		Female		Total	
	Male		No.	%	No.	%
Sulu State College Laboratory High School	No.	%	No.	%	No.	%
Sulu State College Laboratory High School	13		37		50	33.3
Notre Dame of Jolo for Girls	0		50		50	33.3
Notre Dame of Jolo High School-Kasulutan	28		22		50	33.3
Total	41	27.3	109	72.7	150	100

On the other hand, table 1.2 shows the Family Income of the respondents. 47.3 percent (47.3%) of the respondents' family income is classified between Php 10,000 to Php 29,999; 27.3 percent (27.3%) of income is between Php 5,000 to Php 9,999; 21.3 percent (21.3%) of income is between Php 30,000 to Php 59,999; and only 4 percent (4%) is at Php 60,000 and above.

Table 1.2 Profile of the Respondents according to their Parents' Income

Income Classification	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Php 5,000 – Php 9,999	41	27.3	27.3
Php 10,000 – Php 29,999	71	47.3	74.7
Php 30,000 – Php 59,999	32	21.3	96.0
Php 6,000 – above	6	4.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	

The second problem in this study was, “*What are the different factors influencing the study habits of the respondents in Science?*”. Under this question, there were four factors being considered, namely, Home, School, Teacher and Peer.

Table 2.1 showed that the respondents generally rated “Moderately Agree” with a weighted mean of 3.32 and standard deviation of 0.45 but indicated rating of “Agree” on item 1, “I keep my Science notebook and book in a place accessible for me when I need them.” ($\bar{x} = 4.23$; $SD = 0.94$); item 2, “Our house is conducive for learning/studying especially at night.” ($\bar{x} = 3.83$; $SD = 0.90$); item 7, “I ask help from my mother/father or brother/sister if I do not understand some parts of my lesson.” ($\bar{x} = 3.70$; $SD = 1.20$); and item 9, “There are other books/materials in our home which I can use for my assignments.” ($\bar{x} = 3.96$; $SD = 1.12$)

The finding is consistent with the study conducted by Adeyemi and Adeyemi (2014) stating that parents are the custodians of their children’s education. Their attitude to education of their children may make their (children) educational attainment. Additionally, Jayaswal et. Al (2003) in their study found that parents of high achievers exerted significantly more, supporting their children’s studies than the parents of low achiever students.

Table 2.1 Factors Influencing the Study Habits of the Respondents classified as to Home

Statements	Population	Mean	SD	Description
1. I keep my Science notebook and book in a place accessible for me when I need them.	150	4.23	0.94	Agree
2. Our house is conducive for learning/studying especially at night.	150	3.83	0.90	Agree
3. I have an arranged time to study my lessons every night.	150	3.47	0.87	Moderately Agree
4. The other members of my family bother me when I am trying to study.	150	2.57	1.27	Moderately Agree
5. I relax and get a good sleep the night before an important examination.	150	3.22	1.32	Moderately Agree
6. I have a habit of daydreaming when I am studying.	150	3.15	1.27	Moderately Agree
7. I ask for help from my mother/ father or brother/sister if I do not understand some parts of my lesson.	150	3.70	1.20	Agree
8. I study my lessons where I can also watch television or listen to music.	150	2.95	1.25	Moderately Agree
9. There are other books/materials in our home which I can use for my assignments.	150	3.96	1.12	Agree
10. I have a lot of assigned household chores to do after school that make me tired and I can no longer study.	150	2.61	1.11	Moderately Agree
11. Often times, there is nobody at home that I can consult for difficult assignments and lessons.	150	2.85	1.18	Moderately Agree
12. We have computer/internet connections at home that I can use to study.	150	3.33	1.41	Moderately Agree
Weighted Average		3.32	0.45	Moderately Agree

Table 2.2 displayed the weighted mean of 3.56 and standard deviation of 0.45 described as, “Agree” which implies that, generally, the respondents agreed to the statements on factors influencing the study

habits of the respondents classified according to school, but with “Moderately Agree” of item 4, “I consult my teacher for suggestions on how to make better progress.” ($\bar{x} = 3.33$; $SD = 0.98$); item 6, “I borrow Science books in the library for references and review purposes.” ($\bar{x} = 3.08$; $SD = 1.11$); item 7, “My mind is on to other things when new and difficult lessons are explained.” ($\bar{x} = 2.84$; $SD = 1.12$); and item 8, “I pay attention in class only when I am called to recite.” ($\bar{x} = 2.61$; $SD = 1.21$).

This finding is parallel with the study of Palacio (2011) which stated that students who develop good study habits at school increase the potential to complete their assignments successfully and to learn the material they are studying. It was also stated by Quimbo (2010) as cited by Suan (2012) that, by effectively providing materials in school, can improve academic achievement. The mere presence of learning materials such as books, charts, visual aids and others affect the learning outcomes.

Table 2.2 Factors Influencing the Study Habits of the Respondents classified as to School

Statements	Population	Mean	SD	Description
1. I clarify things to my teacher if they are not clear to me.	150	3.71	0.96	Agree
2. I keep my corrected test papers for review purposes.	150	3.67	1.01	Agree
3. I take down notes.	150	4.15	0.97	Agree
4. I consult my teacher for suggestions on how to make better progress.	150	3.33	0.98	Moderately Agree
5. I feel that I have to try hard in my studies.	150	4.36	0.79	Agree
6. I borrow Science books in the library for references and review purposes.	150	3.08	1.11	Moderately Agree
7. My mind is on to other things when new and difficult lessons are explained.	150	2.84	1.12	Moderately Agree
8. I pay attention in class only when I am called to recite.	150	2.61	1.21	Moderately Agree
9. The school has available books and other references in the library.	150	4.27	0.89	Agree
10. The school has materials needed for activities in Science.	150	3.54	1.01	Agree
Weighted Average		3.56	0.45	Agree

Table 2.3 disclosed the weighted mean of 4.48 and standard deviation of 0.57, rated “Agree” on the factors influencing the study habits of the respondents classified according to teacher. This implies that the respondents agreed with all items on factors influencing the study habits according to teacher, especially on item 1, “The teacher delivers the lesson in a manner that the students understand easily.” ($\bar{x} = 4.56$; $SD = 0.68$); item 3, “The teacher encourages the students to ask questions for clarifications.” ($\bar{x} = 4.74$; $SD = 0.63$); item 4, “The teacher gives enough examples for each topic.” ($\bar{x} = 4.53$; $SD = 0.73$); item 6, “The teacher is available for consultation about the lessons.” ($\bar{x} = 4.563$; $SD = 0.79$); item 8, “The teacher gives assignment.” ($\bar{x} = 4.53$; $SD = 0.75$); and item 9, “The teacher gives back the test paper after checking.” ($\bar{x} = 4.48$; $SD = 0.57$) which were rated as “Strongly Agree”.

The result is congruent with the study conducted by Oldfather and McLaughlin (1993) cited by Adeyemi (2014) which revealed that, students are motivated to learn in classroom where teachers impress the students that they can make it, where teachers praise and encourage students for efforts made and where teachers encourage students not only to compete with others but also to compete themselves.

Table 2.3 Factors Influencing the Study Habits of the Respondents classified as to Teacher.

Statements	Population	Mean	SD	Description
1. The teacher delivers the lesson in a manner that the students understand easily.	150	4.56	0.68	Strongly Agree
2. The teacher presents the lesson briefly.	150	4.39	0.84	Agree
3. The teacher encourages the students to ask questions or clarifications.	150	4.74	0.63	Strongly Agree
4. The teacher gives enough examples for each topic.	150	4.53	0.73	Strongly Agree
5. The teacher explains the answers of his examinations.	150	4.13	1.03	Agree
6. The teacher is available for consultation about the lessons.	150	4.53	0.79	Strongly Agree
7. The teacher has a sense of humor that makes the classroom situation light.	150	4.31	0.88	Agree
8. The teacher gives assignments.	150	4.53	0.75	Strongly Agree
9. The teacher gives back the test papers after checking.	150	4.63	0.75	Strongly Agree
Weighted Average		4.48	0.57	Agree

Table 2.4 showed a weighted mean of 3.55 and standard deviation of 0.70, rated as “Agree”. This revealed that the respondents generally agreed with all the statements for the factors influencing the study habits of the respondents classified according to peer, except item 3, “I prefer chatting with friends than studying at night.” ($\bar{x} = 2.17$; $SD = 0.96$) which was rated as “Disagree”.

This finding is the same with the finding of the study of Adika and Toyobo (2007) which reported that, both peer influence and pupil’s interest correlate significantly with academic achievement. It was also asserted by Salleh (2011) that, students were not negatively influenced by their peers in decision – making, but, that peer gives positive influence on their achievement in academics and make them differentiate wrong and right; while Oleyed and Olatoye (2005) said that there was no significant relationship between peer influence and study habit.

Table 2.4 Factors Influencing the Study Habits of the Respondents classified as to Peer.

Statements	Population	Mean	SD	Description
1. It is more fun to study with friends than alone at home.	150	3.51	1.31	Agree
2. Doing activities with friends yields to better output.	150	4.06	1.00	Agree
3. I prefer chatting with friends to studying at night.	150	2.17	0.96	Disagree
4. Encouragement coming from a friend to study hard is indeed an inspiration.	150	4.09	0.92	Agree
5. Misunderstanding with friends bothers me even when I am at home.	150	3.74	1.19	Agree
6. I learn a lot in a group study.	150	3.72	1.15	Agree
Weighted Average		3.55	0.70	Agree

The third research question in this study is, “*Is there significant difference on the study habits of the respondents when data are classified according to gender and parents’ income?*”.

Table 3.1 showed that there is a significant difference between study habits of the respondents when classified according to gender. An F-test of -19.45 with a significant value of 0.000 indicated a significant difference.

This result is congruous with the result of the study conducted by Awodun (2014) which found that there is significant gender difference in attitude towards, and interest in science, with girls losing interest faster than boys in secondary school. These gender differences were most likely to be connected with a number of variables. This is also true, with the research conducted by Tural (2013) where he found that, male students have more positive study habits for Physics than female students.

Table 3.1 Difference between Study Habits of the Respondents classified according to Gender.

	Paired Difference						
	Mean	SD	Std. Error Mean	F-test	df	Sig.	Decision
Gender Study Habit	-1.37	0.73	.057	-19.045	149	.000	Significant

Table 3.2 revealed that there is significant difference between the study habits of the respondents when classified according to parents' income. This is manifested in the F-test value of 7.718 at significant value of .000.

This finding is in parallel with the result of the research conducted by Kingdom (1996) where he identified family economic status as being significantly related to academic achievement, for example, according to him, low caste pupils have significantly lower achievement than their non – low caste colleagues, even after controlling for parental education and household wealth.

Table 3.2 Difference between Study Habits of the Respondents classified according to Parents' Income.

	Paired Difference						
	Mean	SD	Std. Error Mean	F-test	df	Sig.	Decision
Parents' income Study Habit	.609	0.97	.079	7.718	149	.000	Significant

The fourth question in this study is, *“Is there significant difference between the study habits of the respondents and their academic achievement in Science?”*.

The result showed that there is a significant difference between study habits of the respondents and their academic achievement. Table 4 disclosed that the t-test 309.17 at significant value of .000 suggested “Significant difference.”

The result is agreeable with the study of Ansari (1980) where he found that study attitudes are both significant variables which determine the academic performance of the students. Abid (2006) in his research revealed that guidance services have significant positive effect on student's study attitudes and study habits. Improvement in study attitude and study habits, he added resulted in improvement of students' academic achievement.

Table 4 Difference between Study Habits and Academic Achievement of the Respondents

	Paired Difference						
	Mean	SD	Std. Error Mean	F-test	df	Sig.	Decision
Academic Achievement Study Habit	8.57	3.39	0.277	309.17	149	.000	Significant

CONCLUSION

A good study habit helps a student to achieve academic success. In the development of a good study habit, there are factors to be taken into consideration, and these factors were involved in this study, home, school, teacher and peer.

Based on the result of this study, it can be noted that, indeed, the study habits of a student are influenced by the different factors, such as home, school, teacher and peer. The gender of a student, as well as his parents' income, affect his study habit. The academic achievement of a student is affected by the student's study habit as well.

Analyzing the result of the study conducted, it was found out that, there is a significant difference on the study habits of the respondents in Science when their profile (gender and parents' income) is considered. This implies that gender of the respondents as well as their parents' income affect their study habits and eventually their performance at school and their academic achievement. Furthermore, a significant difference on the study habits of the respondents in Science and their academic achievement was revealed in the study. This means that the study habits of a student affect his academic achievement. Having a good study habit yields positive academic achievement while poor study habit yields poor academic achievement.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the result of the data gathered, the following suggestions were formulated:

- (1) Parents must not only support their children financially but also emotionally and morally. Parents should find time to be with their children and discuss matters regarding their studies;
- (2) School administrators should allow/send their teachers to trainings and seminars that they may be equipped with the necessary knowledge and skills needed in the teaching process. School administrators must continuously provide learning and teaching materials necessary in the learning process of the students as well;
- (3) Teachers must not only develop the heads (mental ability) of the students, but also their hearts (emotional ability) and hands (service) to help them become productive and better members of the society;
- (4) Students must be careful in selecting their group of friends and should not allow their friends influence them to neglect or take for granted their studies. They must also bear in mind that, no matter how their environment would like to help them, if they themselves would not help their own selves, no success could be achieved; and
- (5) This study may serve as an avenue for further studies.

REFERENCES

- Abid H (2006) Effect of Guidance Services on Study Attitudes, Study Habits and Academic Achievement of Secondary School Students. *Bulletin of Education and Research*, June 2006 Vol. 28 No. 1 pp. 35 – 45.
- Acido MB (2010) High School Students' Reasoning Skills and their Study Habits and attitudes towards Learning. Retrieved from journals.upd.edu.ph
- Adesemowo PO (2000). Some Psycholo. Ingredients in the Education Preparation of Youth in Contemporary Nigeria. *8(1):145-194*
- Adesoji FA, Oladelle O (2003). Student and teacher related variables as determination of secondary school students' academic achievement in Chemistry in Lagos State Nigeria.

- Adeyemi, Abisola Moradeyo and Adeyemi, Semiu Babatunde (2014) Personal factors as predictors of students' Academic Achievement in Colleges of Education in Southwestern Nigeria. February 23, 2014. Retrieved from *Academic journals Vol. 9(4) 97-10*.
https://www.academia.edu/84706235/Personal_factors_as_predictors_of_students_academic_achievement_in_colleges_of_education_in_South_Western_Nigeria
- Ansari ZA (1980) Study Habits and Attitudes of Students. Development and Validation of Questionnaires Measures. Islamabad National Institute of Psychology
- Aquino GV (2001). Educational Management. *Rex Bookstore Inc. pp. 190-191*
- Awodun AO and Kenni Am (2014) Influence of Peer Group on Students' Motivation and Academic Performance of Chemistry Students in secondary Schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. Retrieved from
<https://www.ijojournals.com/index.php/er/article/download/462/224>
- Burke MA and Sass T (2008). Classroom Peer Effort and Students Achievement. *Urban Institute Publicaffairs@urban.org*
- Good CV (ed. 1973). Dictionary of Education. (3rd Edition). New York: McGrawHill Book Company.
- Hughes JE (2014). How to develop good study habits. *Phoenix forward: Student life*
- Irilis JA (2005) Factors Affecting the Study Habits of the Sixth Graders of Riverside Elementary School. Thesis, Sulu State College
- Jayaswal et.al (2003) Retrieved from Shodhganga.inflibnet
- Kingdom CG (1996) The quality and Efficiency of Public and Private Schools: a case Study of Urban India. *Oxford Bull. Econ. Statist. 58(1): 55-80*
- Olayede DO and Olatoye RA (2005) Peer Influence on the Study Habit of Secondary Students
- Oldfather P, McLaughlin J (1993). Gaining and losing voice: a longitudinal study of students continuing impulse to learn across elementary and middle level contexts. *Res. Middle Level Educ.17(1):1-25*.
- Palacio JR (2011, September 25) Helping Students Develop Good Study Habit. Retrieved from [sthud_habit.doc](https://www.researchpublish.com/upload/book/A%2520Study%2520of%2520Academic%2520Achievement-7879.pdf).
<https://www.researchpublish.com/upload/book/A%2520Study%2520of%2520Academic%2520Achievement-7879.pdf>
- Quimbo SLA (2010) Explaining Math and Science Achievement of Public School Children in the Philippines. *Philippine Review of Economics, 40(2)*
- Salleh MJ (2011) Peer Influence in academic achievement and Behavior among Students of Maria Science College Malaysia. National Seminar on Counselling across Culture. Retrieved from
<https://ropiicimedu>
- Siegler R (2006). How Children Develop. Exploring Child Development. *Student Media Tool kit and Scientific American Reader. New York Worth Publisher.*
- Suan (2012) Factors Affecting Underachievement in Mathematics. Retrieved from www.kuis.edu.my
- Tural G (2013) Determining of High School Students' Study Habits for Physics. Retrieved from *Balkan Physics Letters © Bogazici University Press*